

Importance of English Language in Present Epoch

Mehrajuddin, Showkat Hussain Wani

Research scholar Barkatullah University Bhopal.

Email: ¹mehrajeng146@gmail.com , ²Showkathussainwani507@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT:

As human beings, we need to communicate in order to get acquaintance. Communication is the essence of human beings that definitely needs a tool to happen it. So, human beings use language as a means of communication .It urges people to acquire English language frequently. English is the only language that is almost used in all fields like education, science, information and technology, internet, medicine, business, engineering, tourism and so on. As a language ,English attains the global status due to its usage and being lingua franca.The trait of lingua franca does not only make communication a lot easier but formation of English as bridge or common language among the people of diverse speech as well. The present paper mainly highlights the importance of English language, its application, and various benefits in our day to day life.

Key words; Language, global, education, internet, importance, lingua franca, application.

Introduction:

It is universally accepted fact that language is the primary source of communication. It is the basic tool through which we share our ideas, opinions, knowledge, experience, thoughts etc effectively with others. To understand any sort of context, it is only language that makes it happen. So, keeping it in mind, the importance of English language cannot be denied and ignored as it makes our access to every corner of the world. It helps to maintain international relationship in education, science, business, travel and what not.

Application and Benefits of English Language:

English language teaching and learning have, over the years, assumed great significance, especially in the context of globalization, advances in information technology and the use of the internet. Communication in English between people from different countries and continents has increased phenomenally in the recent past. (Aslam, Mohammad etal, Introduction to English phonetics and phonology,).English plays a dominant role in almost all the fields in the present globalized world. At present the entire world has become accessible and familiar for all people as English is used as a common language. English does not only play a role as a communication tool but simultaneously helps us to adapt to the situation. It is pertinent to mention here, that English language is becoming increasingly important both in native and non-native speaking countries .In addition to that, in twenty-first century it becomes dire need to use it both in the sphere of writing as well as spoken form. So, it would be genuine to mention that it opens new avenues in our life to compete in every domain of life.Obviously; it becomes evident to attain proficiency in communicative English In order to be a active part of the society.

The twenty-first century has brought about tremendous changes in the lives of people whether in social, economic or political sphere .It is necessary to know about the historical background of English language .DICTIONARY OF LITERARY TERMS (COLES NOTES) highlights its background as` the English language developed from the west Germanic dialects spoken by the Angles, Saxons and other Teutonic tribes who gradually invaded and occupied England in the fifth and sixth centuries. The word English reflects the fact that Anglo-Saxon literature first flourished in the north and was written in the Anglican dialects spoken in Northumbria and Mercia. Later, under King Alfred, the West Saxon region became the cultural center. The earlier Anglian literature was copied in the West Saxon dialect, now commonly called old English, or Anglo-Saxon.'

In order to know properly why learning English is so important, we definitely need to go through these lines mentioned in website www.british-study.com that `Nowadays, more and more people are dedicating time to studying English as a second language .Many countries include English in their school syllabus and children are starting to learn English at a younger and younger age. But what is the true value of learning English?

Whether you are looking for a new job or planning to travel the world, studying English can help you progress in life both personally and professionally. You can compete in the global job market, increase your career skills and start to meet people around the world ...'

Owlcation.com a website highlights its importance as ` language is our primary source of communication; it's how we share ideas with others. Some people even say that language is what separates us from animals and makes us human....Six reasons why English is important

1. it's an international common tongue
2. it's the language of academia

3. It gives you access to a wealth of written media, online and printed.
4. It comes in handy when travelling.
5. It's essential if you want to work in international business or commerce etc.

Apart from above mentioned things, English language plays a key role in the field of information and in media and entertainment as highlighted by M.Samanth Reddy, lecturer English, Koti, Hyderabad under the paper 'importance of English language in today's world':

For information: In today's world of information superhighway, English is essential for getting easy access to any information. Almost any information is available in English. English is the language of information technology and internet.

In Media and Entertainment: English is important for access to world media and entertainment. Satellite channels around the world telecast news and views in English. Games and sports are telecast live and their commentaries are also broadcasted in English...

Conclusion

Keeping the above mentioned objectives in consideration, we can conclude to very least that English language is really one of the most used and dominant languages in the whole world. It helps connect us to the global world. In addition, it helps us in our professional life. It is fact that learning English is a big challenge and an act of toiling, but once acquainted with it can really become beneficial and can create different opportunities in our life span. It would be suffice here to mention that English is known as lingua franca due to its abundance use and influence. Due to its wide domain, it is considered as bridge language, link language or simply common language.

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